

THE USING OF FIGURATIVE WORDS AND EXPRESSIONS IN ENGLISH DAILY LIFE SPEECH

Guzal Ismatova

Master student. Bukhara state university, Linguistics: English

Abstract

Whether you're planning to write something, in particular, figurative language is what offers introduced color to your writing. With the assistance of figurative language, it will make dull and normal writings greater insightful and effective. It helps draw attention to readers as it amplifies the idea of what you are trying to attain to your audience. If you're a teacher, a copywriter, or you're in a enterprise entity writing emails to your clients, figurative language can help you describe some thing via comparing it to some thing else. As you read along with this article, we'll outline what figurative language is, identify its importance in everyday conversation and provide you examples of how it can assist in your daily life speech.

Introduction

Language is very vital to human lives. It is a machine of traditional spoken, manual, or written symbols by using capacity of which human beings, as members of a social group. By using language, human beings can narrate and share their trip to others and tell some activities in the omit and can find out about the necessary things from those activities to be better in future by using language. It makes humans are easy to speak with other one. It performs role in dialog as a social interplay instrument amongst people. It means that language can't be separated from human life because language has necessary role.

Figurative language serves as an terrific communication tool and is something we come across every day that helps us carry complicated descriptions or thoughts quickly and effectively. Also referred to as "figures of speech," figurative language can be utilized to persuade, interact and join with an target audience and enlarge

your meant message. Implementing figurative language takes some cautious idea and shut observations to successfully deliver your meant meaning. In this article, we overview some common sorts of figurative language and consider some examples to deepen your understanding.

In general, figurative language is that kind of language which departs from the language employed in the traditional, literal ways of describing person or objects or situation. Using figurative language is making imaginative description in fresh way. Fresh way means adding effects to the figurative without deviating the real meaning of the figurative. Figurative language describes many devices of language that allow people to speak non-literally, to say one thing and mean another. It always makes people to notice a comparison between the thing that is disparate or different.¹

Its creative wording is used to build imagery to deepen the audience's understanding and help provide power to words by using different emotional, visual and sensory connections.

1. Figurative language is used to:
2. Compare two unlike ideas to increase understanding of one
3. Describe ideas sometimes difficult to understand
4. Show a deeper emotion or connection
5. Influence the audience
6. Help make connections
7. Make descriptions easier to visualize
8. Elicit an emotion²

Figurative language makes use of phrases or expressions with a which means that is distinctive from the literal interpretation. Figurative language is produced in our daily conversation and regularly observed in literary works, such as newspaper,

¹ S. Angel "Analysis of Metaphor Used in Speaking of XI Grade Students at SMA" YAPIM Medan.2018

²<https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/figurative-language-examples>

advertisements, novels, poems, and so on. “Figurative language can provide a useful springboard for integrated skills work and to stimulate reading, speaking, and writing skills”.³ The characteristic of figurative language is to stimulate a certain image. It influences the language splendor of work in each oral and written conversation.

Materials and methods.

We observe different kind of English movies and cartoons to find some examples of figurative words. And we know the most used figurative words. There are 5 main types of figurative word and expressions. They are used in everyday life of people to make their sentence more attractive, fluent, expressive, and interactive. One by one we see how they are utilized in conversation of people who live in ordinary life.

- Metaphor
- Simile
- Hyperbola
- Personification
- Symbolism

Metaphors denote a literary figure that looks deep that it doesn't make sense. You would only understand them when you can completely hold close the connection between the phrases used in comparing two things. Metaphor is a part of figurative language the use of an analogy or close comparison between two things that are now not normally treated as if they had whatever in common. Metaphor is frequent capacity of extending the uses and references of words. “Metaphors are

³ Lazar, G. (2003). Meaning and metaphors. Cambridge: Cambridge University press

common in language use, and ordinarily it does not seem to require any particular effort to construct and understand them.”⁴

Metaphor is a kind of figurative language to think something analogy. Here is the example of metaphor: You are the beautiful wealth sent by God to me. The example above can be said as a metaphor because it is constructed on the spot by the author to give an illustration of his feeling that his girlfriend is compared with beautiful wealth which is related to his imagination only. It is one which is understood only after paying special attention to the comparison between wealth in real context as noun and in its context is his girlfriend. There is comparison meaning between you and wealth. But in this context compare that You as human with wealth as noun.⁵

Metaphors directly compare two subjects. Metaphor is a figure of speech which concisely compares two things by saying that the one is the other.⁶

We can see the other examples which are taken from daily conversation:

- One famous example is “Time is gold.” Time is not made of gold, however the cost of time is as treasured as gold.

- Love, you are my sunshine.
- The gladiator has a heart of stone, and he’s drowning in a sea of grief.
- My friend is undergoing a rollercoaster of emotions.
- Love is a battlefield.

Simile is another type of figurative words. What is a simile? It compares two things and makes use of the phrase “like” or “as.” They are often used in normal every day conversations. Simile ambitions to stir an interesting connection in the thinking of who you’re talking to. Simile is the simplest kind of figurative language

⁴ Alm-Arvius, C. (2003). Figures of speech. Sweden: Student litterature AB.

⁵ Bertaria Sohnata Hutauruk "THE USE OF FIGURATIVE LANGUAGES ON THE STUDENTS" POETRY SEMESTER V AT FKIP UNIVERSITAS HKBP NOMMENSEN" University of HKBP Nommesen Received on 12 April 2019 / Approved 24 April 2019

⁶ McArthur, Tom. 1992. The Oxford Companion to the English Language. New York: Oxford University Press.

to certain something. Here the example of simile from Lazar: My life is like empty room without your coming. The kind of figurative language is simile. It can be clearly and easily seen that the data uses simile as a kind of figurative language because the statement above use Like as a characteristic of simile. By using simile, the word like empty room is an utterance of somebody who declares his life becomes zero without his girlfriend.⁷

“Simile is an expression that describes something as being similar to something else, using words „as or like”.⁸

There are examples which are taken from real life:

- The new coach is as tall as a giraffe.
- Strong as an ox
- Clean as a whistle
- Busy as a bee
- Brave as a lion
- Clear as mud

Hyperbole

Hyperbole is an excessive exaggeration that objectives to prove a point. While it's ordinarily humorous or ridiculous, it brings out a experience of humor to the reader or the one listening. Though the exaggeration is outrageous, Hyperbole adds coloration to any assertion or conversation. “ Hyperbole is exaggeration or overstatement. The exaggeration is so great that others are not able to take the statement literally. Hyperbole is an exaggeration or over statement, usually deliberate and not meant to be taken literally”.⁹

We can see some examples of it:

⁷ Bertaria Sohnata Hutauruk"THE USE OF FIGURATIVE LANGUAGES ON THE STUDENTS" POETRY SEMESTER V AT FKIP UNIVERSITAS HKBP NOMMENSEN" University of HKBP Nommesen Received on 12 April 2019 / Approved 24 April 2019

⁸ Lazar, G. (2003). Meaning and metaphors. Cambridge: Cambridge University press

⁹ Larson, M.L.1998. Meaning-based Translation. Lanham: University Press of America Inc

- He snores like a freight train.
- I have told her a million times to clean the room.
- He's so thin that the wind can carry him away.
- Today it's so bright that even the sun would have to wear sunglasses.
- She rushed out of the room in floods of tears crying a lot
- Let's have dinner, I am starving very hungry.
- When she was in Paris, she spent ton of money lot of money.¹⁰

Personification

Personification is typically used in fiction, poetry, and rhymes, and it attributes human characteristics to inanimate animals, objects, or ideas. Using this determine of speech can broaden the reader's imagination. Personification is a part of figurative language that is giving the attribute of human beings to animal, an object or a concept. It is sub type of metaphor, an implied assessment in which the figurative time period of the evaluation is constantly human being. "Personification is a kind of figurative language which describes lifeless thing as if has human being nature".¹¹

The example: How poor are words in conveying the heights of splendor.

The example above can be said as a personification because in the real context the word. Conveying always refers to the human action which is used anatomy such Mouth to speak an utterance to somebody. But by looking the data above that it is used a personification because the word poor words as if a human being which has a nature such able to describe a human action in conveying something. But it is totally a thing which can be a human being as called personification.¹²

Examples:

- The moon smiles at us.
- The trees are waving to the tiger.

¹⁰ QURROTUL AIN "AN ANALYSIS OF FIGURATIVE LANGUAGE IN THE SONG LYRICS BY MAHER ZAIN"

¹¹ Keraf, G. (2009). *Diksi dan gaya bahasa*. Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.

¹² Bertaria Sohnata Hutauruk "THE USE OF FIGURATIVE LANGUAGES ON THE STUDENTS" POETRY SEMESTER V AT FKIP UNIVERSITAS HKBP NOMMENSEN"University of HKBP Nommesen

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- The wind touched my skin.
- The car halted with a screaming complaint.
- The TV stared at me.
- The sky was filled with thousands of dancing stars.
- Opportunity knocked at her door.

Symbolism

You'll be aware of its symbolism when a phrase has its definition but demonstrates something definitely different. It's like the use of artwork to symbolize an idea. This is typically used when authors desire to show a positive emotion or mood. There are given some of them:

- Inserting a red rose in your writings to show love
- Using an owl to symbolize wisdom
- Incorporating an apple pie to demonstrate a traditional American lifestyle
- Showing the image of the American flag to represent patriotism.

Results.

We define the following types of figurative words and expressions most used in English culture and their daily life speech. The examples are taken from internet sites, and movies and they describe English daily life conversation.

Here are some common examples of symbolism in everyday life:

rainbow—symbolizes hope and promise

red rose—symbolizes love and romance

four-leaf clover—symbolizes good luck or fortune

wedding ring—symbolizes commitment and matrimony

red, white, blue—symbolizes American patriotism

green traffic light—symbolizes “go” or proceed

tree blossoms—symbolize spring season

Pilgrim hat—symbolizes Thanksgiving holiday

dollar sign—symbolizes money, earnings, wealth

image of shopping cart—symbolizes online purchases.

Similes are regularly used in the language people use to talk to each other, so characters need not be poets to believably use figurative language. Some similes are used so frequently they are sometimes categorized as clichés. Some examples:

Fit as a fiddle.

Happy as a clam.

She is an old flame.

Dull as dishwater.

Sharp as a tack.

Silent as the grave.¹³

Metaphors come up often in everyday figures of speech and colloquial turns of phrase. Examples of metaphors can be found in everyday life. Below is a list of common metaphors found in the English language:

Blanket of snow: This common phrase compares a layer of snow to a soft, fluffy blanket.

Better half: Many people use this phrase to refer to their significant other. It metaphorically implies that two individuals are part of one body by nature of their union.

Slippery slope: This phrase warns of impending danger initiated by a few small steps.

Roller coaster of emotions: This phrase connects a mercurial emotional state with the ups and downs of an amusement park roller coaster.

Late bloomer: A common metaphor that draws a link between aging and a blooming flower.

Beating a dead horse: This phrase likens a redundant action to the unnecessary wounding of a dead animal.

¹³ <https://www.thebalancecareers.com/how-to-use-everyday-metaphors-and-similes-in-your-fiction-1277707>

Heart of stone: This description can be applied to someone who is unfeeling and cold.

Couch potato: This metaphor draws a link between a sedentary person and a potato.

Melting pot: This image is often used to describe a culture or place where people from a diverse array of backgrounds unite.

Black sheep: This draws a link between a member of a group who doesn't fit in and an anomalous sheep with black wool in a herd of common white sheep.

Personification example:

- My Phone Yells At Me When It's Time To Go To Bed At Night.

Phones cannot yell.

- The Tree Waved Its Leaves To Say, "Hello."

Trees are not going to say anything. Also, waving implies using hands.

- The Last Piece Of Cake Is Calling My Name.

Cake cannot verbally call you.

- The Cactus Stood At Attention While The Soldiers Drove By.¹⁴

This sentence brings to mind the image of a cactus standing tall and saluting, which it cannot do.

Many people use hyperbole as a figure of speech to make something seem larger or more important than it actually is. Such exaggeration or distortion can help express strong emotion, emphasize a point, or even evoke humor. Here are some common examples of hyperbole in everyday speech:

I'm so hungry that I could eat a horse.

That purse looks like it cost a million dollars.

I Love You to the moon and back.

He feels buried under a mountain of work.

I'm dying of thirst.

¹⁴ <https://www.masterclass.com/articles/metaphor-examples-from-literature-and-everyday-speech>

That dog is the cutest thing alive.
 She loves him more than life itself.
 This suitcase weighs a ton.

Conclusion

To conclude our article, we can say observing some types of figurative words in English daily conversation proved English people have very rich sense of humor. They use metaphor, simile, symbolism, personification, and hyperbole more than other types of figurative words. We use figurative words to add colour and interest, and to awaken the imagination. Figurative language is everywhere, from classical works like these of Shakespeare or the Bible, to everyday speech, pop music, television and business issues. So utilising them in daily speech is common in English native speaker.

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